

Co-funded by
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content

- PROJECT MEETING IN VIGO **P. 2**
- THE GREEN HIVE **P. 3**
COMMUNITY PLATFORM
- EUROPEAN CONTEST **P. 5**

the project

Green Hive is a Cooperation Partnership in Vocational Education and Training (VET), co-funded by the **Erasmus+ Programme of the EU**. The project, implemented by the Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (Ireland), Lascò (Italy), KEAN (Greece), Femxa (Spain) and Team 4 Excellence (Romania), aims to develop a **European platform-based Ecosystem for Sustainability Education**.

Would you like to learn more? Reach out to us anytime via the project website greenhiveproject.eu if you have any questions or would like more information.

TRANSNATIONAL PROJECT MEETING IN VIGO

»»» SPAIN, MARCH 2025

Last March, we stopped in Vigo, Spain, for an important Transnational Project Meeting (TPM) hosted by our Spanish partner, Femxa Formación. It was a special opportunity not only to strengthen the collaboration between the partners of the GreenHive project, but also to share important results and plan the next strategic steps.

During the meeting, Lascò presented the **Green Hive Community Platform: the beating heart of our digital ecosystem**. The platform – designed to facilitate dialogue and cooperation between young people, educators, trainers, local and international stakeholders – will offer educational resources, tools for co-creating activities, spaces for managing challenges and collaborative events.

The TPM in Vigo was also the ideal moment to define in detail the kick-off of the **European Contest dedicated to the GreenHive ecosystem hubs**: a creative and collaborative challenge in which participants will be called upon to co-create concrete solutions to address environmental challenges, in line with the objectives of the 2030 Agenda.

THE GREEN HIVE COMMUNITY PLATFORM

We're thrilled to launch our **Community Platform**, a collaborative space where education and training providers, innovators, businesses, and local institutions from across Europe come together around a shared mission: advancing **environmental and social sustainability**.

It's a place where ideas turn into action, and where those actions inspire others. Powered by a dynamic, multidisciplinary European network, the platform connects people and organisations committed to building a greener future.

By joining the platform, you'll gain access to **new and innovative ways to learn and collaborate on sustainability**. You'll also have the opportunity to connect with other hubs and stakeholders to amplify your impact.

Our goal: foster an active, engaged community where cross-sector dialogue sparks practical solutions and lasting change.

— WELCOME TO

GreenHive Community Platform

A digital space that connects education and training providers, innovators, businesses and local institutions from across Europe to discuss sustainability issues. Here you can share co-design tools, ideas and good environmental practices, creating synergies for a sustainable future.

LOGIN

REGISTER

— OPEN HUBS

Carol I Commercial College
Romania

2Liceul Tehnologic Nicolae
Dumitrescu Cumpana
Romania

Associazione Akira
Italy

Forum Lex
Italy

Attiva Windows
Passa a Impostazioni p

THE GREEN HIVE COMMUNITY PLATFORM

➤➤➤ BECOME PART OF OUR COMMUNITY!

As a member, you will find:

- Spaces for the exchange of **educational resources and methodologies**
- Examples of **local good practices** that can be replicated in other contexts
- Forums and thematic areas where you can **discuss and generate new solutions**
- **Networking opportunities** between stakeholders in the green world.

The Green Hive Community Platform aims to cultivate a proactive community that drives **real impact through dialogue and collaboration across diverse but interconnected sectors.**

VISIT THE PLATFORM AND **START CONNECTING TODAY!**

EUROPEAN CONTEST FOR GREEN COMBS

»»» Sustainability: New Perspectives for a Wicked Problem

Launched in March 2025, this European competition invites Green Combs hubs — students, VET providers, teachers, trainers, and their local stakeholders — to **collaborate on developing innovative solutions to today's most pressing environmental challenges.**

Using the Green Hive tools and resources, each Comb will:

- Research a chosen sustainability issue
- Collaborate with NGOs, community groups, and policymakers
- Co-design practical solutions
- Present their proposal through a short video, to be featured for public voting on our platform

Key Dates:

- Deadline for submissions: 30 June 2025
- Winning projects announced in September

STAY TUNED! The winning solution will be featured in our e-publication "**Sustainability: New Approaches for a Wicked Problem**", providing a platform to showcase their innovative work to a wider audience. The publication will be widely promoted by the project consortium at the national and European levels.

Would you like to learn more? Download now the competition rules and guidelines:

DOWNLOAD HERE

